

RECOMMENDATIONS FOR THE USE OF FATS

Saitkulov Foziljon Ergashevich¹

Abdukadirov Shaxriyor Akramali o'g'li²

Ashurova Nigora Ixtiyor qizi³

Turapov Javlon Abdujalil o'g'li⁴

Zoxidjonova Aziza Murodjon qizi⁵

¹Tashkent State Agrarian University,

²⁻³⁻⁴⁻⁵Student of Tashkent State Agrarian University

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Annotation: Thesis artiklesTrans Fatty acids are relatively few in nature for example, in milk fat, but they can be formed during the hydrogenation of liquid vegetable oils, i.e. when they harden. In terms of biological effects, trans fatty acids are close to saturated fatty acids.

Key words: Fatty acids, example, phospholipids, daily diet, triglycerides, complex, fatty acids essential acids, linoleic acid, Omega-6 fatty acid, linolenic acid, Omega-3, fatty acid.

INTRODUCTION

Despite the fact that when talking about fats, the terms "fats" and "lipids" are used, in fact, they are not exactly the same thing. Lipids include simple lipids or triglycerides, complex lipids (for example, phospholipids) and cholesterol or cyclic lipids. The term "fats" is used primarily in relation to triglycerides, consisting of three molecules of fatty acids and glycerol. In the daily diet, fats make up 95-98% of lipids. That is why the term "fats" is used in the sense of food energy.

Fats are made up of fatty acids. Dietary fats contain three types of fatty acids:

- saturated fatty acids;
- monounsaturated fatty acids;
- polyunsaturated fatty acids.

Saturated fatty acids predominate in animal fats, such as lard or butter. At room temperature, animal fats are usually in a solid state.

METHODS AND RESULTS

Mono- and polyunsaturated fatty acids are overwhelmingly present in vegetable fats, such as rapeseed oil. The human body is unable to synthesize two polyunsaturated fatty acids (essential acids) – linoleic acid (Omega-6 fatty acid) and linolenic acid (Omega-3 fatty acid), so they need to be obtained with food. The content of these three types of fatty acids in different fats varies.

Fats are needed by the body because:

- they are a concentrated source of energy for the human body. 1 gram of fat gives about 9 kilocalories of energy,

- they participate in the processes of growth and regulation of other vital activity,
- they are sources of essential polyunsaturated fatty acids,
- they supply the human body with fat-soluble vitamins and are needed for their absorption and transportation in the body,
- phospholipids are part of all tissues and cells, most of them are in nerve tissues and brain cells,
- the fat layer formed around the organs protects them from bruises,
- they are necessary for the excretion of bile into the intestine, otherwise it accumulates in the gallbladder, and there is a danger of the formation of gallstones,
- they are needed to remove bile into the intestine, otherwise it accumulates in the gallbladder, and there is a danger of gallstones forming.

CONCLUSION

Dietary fats are necessary because they are carriers of the flavor of food and create a feeling of satiety. Food without fat has a less pronounced taste and smell.

Trans Fatty acids are relatively few in nature (for example, in milk fat), but they can be formed during the hydrogenation of liquid vegetable oils, i.e. when they harden. In terms of biological effects, trans fatty acids are close to saturated fatty acids.

Regulation 2019/649 of the European Union sets a possible maximum limit on the content of industrial trans fatty acids in products. This is a maximum of 2 g of trans fatty acids per 100 g of fat in the product. If a person eats a variety of foods in accordance with the recommendations (i.e. if the share of total fat in the energy received does not exceed 35%, i.e. a maximum of 80 grams of fat per day at 2000 kcal), the amount of trans fatty acids he receives will not harm his body.

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